

Centaurea kilaea – a new species to the flora of Bulgaria

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Abstract: A rare species, endemic to the European part of Turkey: *Centaurea kilaea* Boiss., was found on the dunes at Veleka River Mouth, Southern Black Sea Coast, Bulgaria. This newly found population is a small one – comprising of 43 individuals, participating in the species composition of typical psammophytic vegetation (white dunes). The proximity of the beach at Igneada in Turkey has probably allowed spontaneous dispersal (by wind or maybe ants or seabirds) to the Bulgarian territory. The very limited size and small number of the population, as well as the high dynamics of the coastal strip in this area, call into question its long-term existence in Bulgaria.

Keywords: Asteraceae, coastal dynamic, conservation status, endemic species, psammophytic vegetation, white dunes

Introduction

The genus *Centaurea* L. is well presented worldwide by approximately 300 species, which makes it one of the largest in the Asteraceae family (Dostal, 1976; Bremer, 1994). In Bulgaria, this genus has over than 60 species (Stoyanov et al., 2021). However, several new species have been found in the Bulgarian flora in the last few decades. Such are: *Centaurea pichleri* (Bancheva & Denchev, 2000), *C. jankae* and *C. trinervia* (Petrova, 2007), *Centaurea wagenitziana* (Kit Tan et al., 2009), *C. sakarensis* (Bancheva & Raimondo, 2013), *Centaurea formanekii* (Dimitrov, 2013) and *C. angelescui* (Stoyanov, 2017).

During a field study on the project KP-06-H84/5-16.12.2024 “Mapping and Spatiotemporal Analysis of Beach-Dune Systems on the Southern Bulgarian Black Sea Coast: Evolution, Anthropogenic Pressure, and Ecological Risks to Dune Habitats”, new to Bulgaria *Centaurea* species: *C. kilaea* Boiss., was found on the dunes at Veleka River Mouth, Burgas

District. This species was recorded in the field and also characterised for the first time to the Bulgarian flora in the recent study.

The species is endemic to Turkey-in-Europe, in the following regions: Kırklareli: Kasatura; Istanbul: Domuzdere, Terkos, Kilyos, Yeşilçay; Adapazarı: Karasu; Bolu (Wagenitz, 1975). According to the Red Data Book of Turkish Plants (Ekim et al., 2000), the conservation status of *C. kilaea* is Endangered. Eskin et al. (2013) studied the germination requirements, plant-soil interactions and population biology of the species. There are also studies of the chromosome number and nuclear DNA content of *C. kilaea* (Meriç et al., 2010), the essential oil composition of the species (Polatoğlu et al., 2014), as well as on its reproductive biology (Kartal, 2025).

This species was recorded from southeastern Bulgaria (region of Lyubimets Town) by Velenovsky (1902). However, his materials were later revised by Stojanov & Achtarov (1935) to a variant of *Centaurea inermis* Velen. Based on this revision,

Stojanov et al. (1967), followed by Wagenitz (1975), rejected the probable occurrence of *Centaurea kilaea* in Bulgaria.

Material and methods

The herbarium materials of *Centaurea kilaea* were collected from the so far single discovered locality in Bulgaria. They were deposited in the herbaria of Sofia University (SO) and Bulgarian Academy of Science (SOM). The morphological description of this species is based on Boissier & Buser (1875), Dostal (1976), Wagenitz (1975) and Candan et al. (2016), as well as on personal observations of collected plants. The habitat was characterised based on vegetation plots. The plant communities in the species's habitat were sampled according to the methods of the Zürich-Monpellier phytosociological school (Braun-Blanquet, 1964). Several photographs are presented for the plant's natural environment, also for its flowers, achenes and phyllaries (Figs 1–6).

Result and discussion

General description of the species

Centaurea kilaea Boiss. (Sect. *Acrolophus*), Fl. Or. 3: 643 (1875). Syn: *Acosta kilaea* (Boiss.) Holub in Preslia 46:226 (1974).

Perennial herb with underground stolons and prostrate or ascending stems (25-) 40–80 cm (Fig. 1), with several branches in upper part. Leaves densely white- or grey tomentose; those of sterile rosettes lyrate (or sometimes undivided) to pinnatisect, lower cauline withered at flowering time, median 1–2-pinnatisect with linear lanceolate to lanceolate segments (1-) 2–4 mm broad, terminal slightly larger, upper simple or with 1-2 pairs of lobes near base. Involucre (10-) 12–15 x (5-) 6–8 mm, ovoid; phyllaries (Fig. 2) slightly longitudinally ridged, sparsely arachnoid. Appendages small, pale brown, with (3-) 4–6(-7) cilia on each side (0,5–1,5 mm), ending in a 0,3–0,8 mm mucro. Flowers rose-purple (Fig. 3), marginal slightly radiant. Achenes (3) 3,5–4,5 mm; pappus (3-) 3,5–4 mm (Fig. 4), innermost row short (1,5 mm) or as long as others.

Taxonomically, *C. kilaea* is close to *C. cuneifolia*; the long pappus of the former is the most distinctive

feature. Ecologically and morphologically, *C. kilaea* is also similar to another psammophytic species from Sect. *Acrolophus* (Cass.) DC – *Centaurea arenaria*. However, in this case, the appendage of the former has large hyaline auricles at the base, the lower leaves are 1- to 2-pinnately-dissected, the terminal segment being slightly larger than the lateral ones, while in *Centaurea kilaea* the appendage has no distinct auricles, and the lower leaves are undivided or lyre-shaped. Both species are perennial, but *C. kilaea* has underground stolons and prostrate or ascending stems, with several branchlets in the upper part, while *C. arenaria* is erect or ascending, usually branched below from the middle part of the stem, branches are simple or with short branchlets.

The plant is flowering from June to August; the fruiting is in July–September. The habitat is only the sandy beaches and mobile dunes, between 1 and 20 m alt. According to Kavgaci (2007), in Turkey (Ignea sand dunes), this species is typical for the association *Otantho-Leymetum sabulosi* Géhu & Uslu 1989 on unstable (white) dunes together with species like: *Ammophilla arenaria*, *Eryngium maritimum*, *Leymus racemosus* subsp. *sabulosus*, *Otanthus maritimus*, *Cionura erecta*, etc.

The name of the species comes from the former Byzantine town of Kila, which is now called Kilyos, where the holotypus was collected (Wagenitz, 1975). Therefore, we propose the plant name to be translated in Bulgarian as “Kilska metlichina”.

Distribution in Bulgaria, population data and habitat

The species was found in the Southern Black Sea Coast, N of Sinemorets Village, at the sand dunes near Veleka River Mouth (Fig. 5), Burgas district, in vegetation plots with coordinates: 42.065853 N, 27.97374 E; NG-85. Collected by Magdalena Valcheva and Rossen Tzonev at 21.05.2025, 26.07.2025 and 23.09.2025 (herbarium materials: SOM 179594, SO 108442).

The proximity of the closest locality in Turkey – Ignea beach, has probably allowed spontaneous dispersal (by wind or maybe ants or seabirds) to the Bulgarian territory. The population (Fig. 6) of the newly established locality numbers 43 individuals, which makes it highly endangered from every anthropogenic (touristic) or natural (waves and coastal dynamic) pressures.

Fig. 1. Common view of *Centaurea kilaea* (July 2025). Photo M. Valcheva.

Fig. 3. Flowers of *Centaurea kilaea* (July 2025). Photo M. Valcheva.

Fig. 2. Phyllaries and appendages of *Centaurea kilaea* (July 2025). Photo M. Valcheva.

Fig. 4. Achenes of *Centaurea kilaea* (July 2025). Photo M. Valcheva.

The habitat is a mobile (white) dune, which has typical psamphytic vegetation (Fig. 5). Such psamphytic species, which are accompanying the population of *Centaurea kilaea*, are: *Elymus farctus*, *Calystegia soldanella*, *Eryngium maritimum*, *Stachys maritima*, *Pancratium maritimum*, *Euphorbia paralias*. However, there are also some ruderals, such as: *Chondrilla juncea*, *Eryngium campestre*, *Echium italicum*.

Conclusion

This species, newly discovered for the flora of Bulgaria, has a very limited distribution in the country. Its population is very small and limited to an area of less than 1,000 square meters. In addition, this population inhabits naturally a highly dynamic substrate, such as the mobile dunes at the mouth of the Veleka River, which are often significantly altered by

Fig. 5. The sand dune, where the population of *Centaurea kilaea* was registered (May 2025). Photo B. Prodanov.

Fig. 6. Part of the population of *Centaurea kilaea* (with red arrows) in its typical habitat (May 2025). Photo M. Valcheva.

the sea. Therefore, in addition to the fact that the species is endangered in Turkey, this makes it even more imperative that the so far only population in

Bulgaria must be protected. We suggest for *Centaurea kilaea* to be included in the Annex III of the Biodiversity Act and therefore to be legally protected in Bulgaria. We also suggest for the species to be evaluated according to the IUCN criteria to Bulgaria as *Centaurea kilaea* Boiss., Critically endangered [B1ab(i iii iv)+2ac(ii iii) D]. On the site, where the population of the species was found, the sand dune had been surrounded by a small wooden fence, which seemed to be quite effective against trampling. The area falls within the borders of natural park “Strandzha” and in protected area “Ustie na reka Veleka”.

Acknowledgements

Financial support of the field study on the project KP-06-H84/5-16.12.2024 “Mapping and Spatiotemporal Analysis of Beach-Dune Systems on the Southern Bulgarian Black Sea Coast: Evolution, Anthropogenic Pressure, and Ecological Risks to Dune Habitats” is gratefully acknowledged.

Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor. As a member of the editorial board Rossen Tzonev recused himself from discussions and decisions on the manuscript.

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